

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS IN THE SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. Physical health improves body function, helps to think better and make decisions. This means that the role of physical education in our life is high. This article describes in detail the importance of physical education and sports in the school education system.

Key words: physical education, physical education, sports competitions, school education system, physical activity, etc.

Teachers exchange experience to improve their skills, organize analysis of each other's lessons. The physical culture team performs the main tasks in the organization of physical education and sports events in educational institutions. Physical education teachers conduct physical education classes and daily physical education activities. Pupils and sportsmen active in physical education and members and leaders of the youth society closely assist physical education teachers in organizing physical education events and sports competitions, holidays, holding walks, excursions and tourism, tourist marches. At the same time, student athletes play an important role in attracting other students to sports and increasing their interest in physical education. All employees of the educational institution must understand the purpose, tasks, content and forms of physical education of pupils and students correctly, participate in practical work based on their activities, physical culture between pupils and parents. and actively promote sports. Physical education teachers must perform the following tasks:

- to ensure that the class passes at a high level and complete the physical education program of the corresponding class;
- together with the doctor, conduct the medical examination of the students on time and take into account the results of the medical examination in their work;
- to ensure that the places where classes are held are kept in appropriate sanitary and hygienic condition;
- all pupils and students should be able to do physical exercises in comfortable clothes;
- participation in the organization and conduct of activities outside the educational institution on physical education and wide involvement of pupils and students in it;
- carrying out explanatory work between parents about the importance of physical education of pupils and students;
- regularly improving the knowledge of pupils and students in the field of physical education;
- to make pupils and students interested in physical culture and to form habits of regular exercise in them.

It is necessary for physical education specialists to know the level of development of physical abilities of the participants, to study individual character traits, moral qualities of intellect, perception, emotional will, and individual differences in static needs. In the process of independent training, pupils' and students' attitude to physical education and sports is formed, the skills of independent exercise, movement and sports are increased. Along with teaching vital movements in independent training, physical qualities such as strength, endurance, flexibility, quickness, and agility are improved. Changes occur in the body as a result of the development of each physical quality. The organs of the

human body are strengthened and the blood circulation develops as a result of improvement. It is to accustom pupils and students to systematic physical exercises not only in educational institutions, but also at home. In order to fulfill this important task, all activities conducted with pupils and students should be lively, the content and form of the studied material should be interesting, exciting, conducted under the sincere treatment of the leader of the activity, the participants should interact with each other. It is necessary to create conditions for cooperation. To attract pupils and students to engage in sports according to their personal interests and physical abilities. Also, it is necessary to carry out general physical training and sports training in the places of residence and sports clubs. Education of organization in pupils and students, preparation of physical culture activities. In order to successfully carry out public physical culture and sports activities in the educational institution, to conduct physical culture classes and trainings in full, students and students need the constant support of the teacher of physical culture activities. Organizers of physical culture, team captains, group leaders in sports circles are elected among pupils and students. They are selected from among active participants. They closely support the physical culture team in the organization and management of physical education and sports events. It is also of great importance in attracting pupils and students to sports and increasing their interest in physical education.

By means of physical education activities, students' movement skills and abilities are formed with the help of walking, running and jumping and throwing and climbing exercises. Positive changes occur and the body becomes healthy with the help of physical exercises and the healing forces of nature, as well as hygienic means, which are considered as means of physical education. Physical education of students is a pedagogical process organized for them to perform physical activities. Physical education work in an educational institution differs in its very diverse forms, which require enthusiasm, initiative, and organization from

pupils and students. They help to develop organizational skills, activity, resourcefulness in students. The purpose of teaching features during physical education and sports training is to teach the requirements of physical development and healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness events will greatly help to master professional training. Physical education activities are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, club activities, sports fitness competitions and holidays. In the organization of physical education, the pedagogical team of the educational institution, especially physical education teachers and sports coaches, is of great importance. The theory of physical education constantly develops and improves based on the practice of physical education. Its methodological basis is always enriched by the assimilation of the results of this practical scientific research. That is why the subject of physical education cannot be frozen, it develops and becomes perfect.

Physical culture and sports are an independent type of human activity, and its importance in the development of society is very great. They significantly affect social production, the development of social relations, and the formation of a person as a person. Nowadays, physical education and sports are very popular. Articles dedicated to sports, books have been written, films dedicated to it, sociologists, doctors, historians, teachers and other experts are paying attention to studying its problems. All this reflects not only the prestige of fashion, but also the place of physical culture and sports in modern society. It is of particular importance to consistently develop a lifestyle in which physical culture and sports are factors in the formation of a well-rounded and well-developed personality. Physical education solves the problems of strengthening health, all-round development of physical and spiritual forces, increasing labor capacity, creative longevity and prolonging the life of people engaged in all spheres of activity. In the process of physical education, the morphological and functional improvement

of the human body, the development of physical qualities, the formation of motor skills, special knowledge systems and their use in public practice and everyday life are carried out. Physical exercises affect labor productivity, they contribute to high creative activity of people engaged in mental work. Conducting regular training with specific sports and physical exercises, using them correctly in the training regime will increase the mental ability of students, develop a number of necessary qualities - depth of thinking, operative, visual and helps improve auditory memory, sensorimotor reactions. Physical education and sports are an important factor in reducing the rate of diseases and injuries in the workplace.

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